

ART EDUCATION AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE FORMATION OF CREATIVE PERSONALITY

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Abstract. Art plays an important role in the creative development of the individual. Art in the learning process creates opportunities for harmonizing the emotional and logical components of students' activities and realizing their creative potential. Art education is a complex-integrated process aimed at realizing the motives, and needs of professional activity, aesthetic perception, and understanding of beauty, which involves the possession of aesthetic knowledge, abilities, skills, the formation of aesthetic judgments, feelings, values, ideals, behavior, certain creative experience and allows successful to carry out professional activities in one or another field. Adherence to certain principles, namely: awareness, dialectical unity, optimality of theory and practice, self-development, reflection, the optimal combination of individual and collective forms of educational and creative activity, and belief in one's strengths and opportunities in the organization of education allows one to develop students' creative abilities. Art education is a continuous process. It lasts throughout a person's life, thanks to which the contradictions between the level of the aesthetic culture of humanity and a certain culture of an individual personality in each period of life are resolved. At the current stage of society's development, professional education needs specialists who not only possess knowledge, abilities, and skills, but are also able to show creative activity and initiative under new, changing conditions.

Keywords: Aesthetic Competence, Aesthetic Education, Art Education, Creative Personality.

Introduction. Human history is a path of struggle to overcome contradictions between material and spiritual, beautiful and ugly, good and evil. Culture has a unique ability to influence a person's spirituality. Attention to art education is natural

because activity in any field cannot be full-fledged today, both without general education and without aesthetic perfection. The lack of a creative component limits the creative abilities of an individual. Art education occupies one of the leading places in pedagogy. Art education forms a spiritually rich personality oriented to universal human values. Spiritual ideals encourage a person to seek for good and positive development. It is an active energy force that organizes the consciousness and activity of the individual, stimulates them to realize the ultimate goal and is, at the same time, a factor in the spiritual development of a person. In its turn, the non-spiritual ideal is characterized by the lack of high cultural and moral qualities, aesthetic needs with a predominance of purely biological ones (Pomytkina et al, 2019).

The National Doctrine of Education Development of Ukraine in the 21st century defines the main goal of education as "the creation of conditions for the development and self-realization of each individual as a citizen of Ukraine, the formation of a generation capable of lifelong learning, creating and developing the values of civil society." That is why personal development is one of the priority directions in the national education system. Personal development is connected with the formation of creative potential, and the development of creative abilities. It is to ensure this process that the ideas and provisions outlined in the state normative legal documents of Ukraine on education issues, namely in the laws of Ukraine "On Education", "On Higher Education", and the State National Program "Education" (Ukraine of the 21st century) are aimed at the "Teacher" Program, the Concept of Education of Children and Youth in the National Education System, the Concept of Artistic and Aesthetic Education of Students in General Educational Institutions, the National Doctrine of Education Development in Ukraine, the National Strategy of Education Development in Ukraine for 2012-2021, etc.

Literature review. In modern theory and practice, the scientific basis for carrying out a complex study of the problem of aesthetic education and the formation of the aesthetic competence of an individual is research in the field of: philosophical (A. Gerasimchuk, I. Ziaziun, V. Kremen, etc.), psychological (I. Bekh, L. Vygotsky, H. Kostiuk, etc.) sciences; professional education (S. Honcharenko, O. Dubasenyuk, S. Lisova, S. Sysoeva); aesthetic education (V. Butenko, O. Demyanchuk, O. Padalka, etc.). The analysis of scientific approaches shows that in the conditions of the transition to new social relations, the issue of aesthetic education of student youth based on ethnicity was investigated by M. Gaidai, P. Ignatenko, M. Leshchenko, O. Piddubna, and others. However, despite the significant interest of scientists in aesthetic culture, values, and aesthetic worldview of the individual, the problem of using ethnographic tools, and researching their role in the educational process for the purpose of forming aesthetic competence has not yet been sufficiently investigated.

Main text. Aesthetic activity is a purposeful process of forming a creatively active personality, capable of perceiving and evaluating the aesthetic in the surrounding reality, nature, art, living, and creating according to the laws of beauty. Aesthetic

competence is an individual's ability to aesthetic perception and understanding of beauty, which implies the possession of aesthetic knowledge, abilities, skills, and the formation of aesthetic judgments, feelings, values, ideals, behavior, etc. Aesthetic competence is a component of personal aesthetic culture. The level of aesthetic competence is closely related to the general cultural level of a person. The formation of aesthetic competence takes place in the process of creative activity of the future teacher, in his aesthetic relationship to the surrounding world, folk art, nature, etc.

Nowadays, the arts are a key component of the curriculum, fostering both creativity and self-expression and recognition of the expression of students (Frank-Witt, 2020; Levy, 1988). The formation of aesthetic competence of an individual is considered by us as a complex integrated process aimed at awareness of motives, needs of professional activity, aesthetic perception, and understanding of beauty, which involves the possession of aesthetic knowledge, abilities, skills, the formation of aesthetic judgments, feelings, values, ideals, behavior, certain creative experience and allows you to successfully carry out professional activities in one or another field.

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Creativity and the ability to create are the main requirements for a modern person living in a world of global changes and integration processes and extremely rapid development of technology and information resources. In the context of such approaches, the disciplines of the artistic and aesthetic cycle acquire special relevance, since their introduction into education is a transformation of education and training into a creative process. The teacher is always in search of modern pedagogical technologies, and optimal, effective ways of influencing the child. The present prompts the teacher to make changes in the system of education, formation, and development of personality with new forms and methods. Only a creative teacher can develop students' creative abilities. Creativity is the process of the birth of something new in nature or man, a necessary condition for the intellectual and spiritual growth of the individual. Scientists from various disciplines consider the creative individual as a person with the ability to solve problems, develop products, and define new topics in each thematic field (Cowan, 2007; Turturică, 2019).

Every person is capable of creativity. And it is a pity that, born with the natural ability to create, the child gradually loses it. Unfortunately, this often happens when creative abilities are not formed in time, and there are no incentives for their

development. One of the most important signs of a creative person is the presence of abilities, which are considered individual and psychological assets of a person, which meet the requirements of creative activity. A creative approach to life is established in childhood and successfully develops throughout life in artistic activity. An individual who thinks creatively is the main driving force of social and spiritual transformations. A creative person adapts much better to social, household, and industrial conditions, and effectively uses, improves, and changes them.

The ability to be creative is one of the most important conditions for the successful self-expression of an individual, its comprehensive self-realization and adaptation in the modern world. The teacher must constantly work on the development of student's creative potential. Adherence to certain principles in the organization of education allows to develop students' creative abilities:

- the principle of awareness lies in the importance of the information a person receives about art, creators, and the results of their work;
- the principle of dialectical unity and optimality of theory and practice. It is important that students move from reflections and stories to practical work;
- the principle of self-development. In the organization of educational and creative activities, it is necessary to rely on the strengths and take into account the weaknesses of the individual. Self-knowledge is of particular importance here;
- the principle of reflection. Reflection helps to relieve physical, intellectual, and emotional stress during complex tasks;
- the principle of optimal combination of individual and collective forms of educational and creative activity. In the implementation of this principle, it is necessary to constantly take into account and correlate the purpose, content, and difficulties of various types of work, methods, and forms of its organization with the peculiarities of the development of students' creative abilities;
- the principle of belief in the person's capabilities. This principle is implemented when a democratic style of communication is followed in the process of managing educational and creative activities, which allows the student to fully realize himself.

During training, teachers should select material that has an educational focus, an aesthetic appearance, and corresponds to the norms of a color image. For example, clarity most fully and most accurately reveals the essence of the phenomena being studied, promotes memorization, draws attention to the material, provides emotional impact and high-quality learning of the material.

When forming creative abilities, interaction with students should be organized so that it includes:

- lack of criticism of unsuccessful creative attempts;
- opportunity for the student to choose and independently set the problem;

- consideration of the student's interests;
- support of creative initiative;
- unconditional positive attitude towards the student;
- emotional contact with the student.

Such interaction allows creating of internal motivation in students during the learning process, which contributes to creative self-expression and the development of their creativity. Certain traditions in art education have developed in our country. An important means of art education is the involvement of student youth in amateur creativity in the field of arts, the centers of which have become out-of-school educational institutions of Ukraine. As a rule, it is on their basis that art collectives become creative laboratories for the creation of new technologies and methods of learning, which contributes to the emergence of new types of extracurricular educational institutions and creative associations. In art education, the leading role belongs to the types and genres of art, as the most effective means of spiritual enrichment of the individual, communication with which is always a creative process.

Conclusion. Aesthetic education of young people involves a qualitative change in the level of their aesthetic culture, which can cover both an individual, a social group, and society as a whole. This is a continuous process throughout a person's life, thanks to which the contradictions between the level of the general aesthetic culture of humanity and a certain culture of an individual personality in each period of life are resolved. So, at the current stage of society's development, professional education needs specialists who not only possess knowledge, abilities, and skills but are also able to show creative activity and initiative under new, changing conditions. Aesthetic education and the formation of aesthetic competence of young people presupposes not only the presence of a sense of beauty in them but also the ability to form the knowledge and skills of students to see and create beauty in the surrounding reality, in particular in folklore, folk crafts, traditions, customs, rituals, to be able to distinguish the beautiful from the ugly, live by the laws of beauty.

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